

THE FRACTURE AND INTERFACE OF Gr/Al COMPOSITES
BY SQUEEZE CASTING

Sui Quanwu, Guo Shuqi and Tang Fengjun
Institute of Metal Research, Academia Sinica
Shenyang, China

ABSTRACT

A new method of the ultrasonic liquid infiltration is employed to manufacture Gr/Al precursor without diffusion barrier coating. The tensile strength is 900 MPa and the modulus is 187 GPa.

Gr/Al composites are produced by LD2 or LD5 alloy heating over 50-80 k of its melting point and then it is squeezed into the preform of Gr/Al precursors which pre-set up in the model. The mechanical properties of Gr/Al composite are determined after heat-treatment by T6. The tensile strength at room temperature is higher than 550 MPa and the modulus is 130 GPa.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) is used to observe the fracture morphology of Gr/Al composite. The transmission electron microscope (TEM) and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) as well as second ion mass spectroscopy (SIMS) are applied to determine the interface structure and reaction products.

The study results appear that during the squeeze casting the preheating temperature of the precursor preform and the liquid temperature of alloy, the pressure stress and constant pressure time are directly relation to the mechanical properties, the fracture morphology and interface reaction. So that Gr/Al composite quality depend upon properly to select the technique parameter.

1. INTRODUCTION

Gr/Al composite have been wonder investigation since the late 1960s. Generally, Gr/Al composites produced by liquid metal infiltration, but molten aluminum has low affinity for the normal graphite fiber, and hence severe infiltration and wetting problems may exist when Gr/Al composite is manufactured. In the past few decades the most widely accepted method that is used to overcome these problems utilized the chemical vapor deposition of titanium carbide and titanium boride coatings onto the graphite fiber[1] which alters the interfacial properties sufficiently so that wetting and infiltration will occur. Not only these methods is complex and detract the environments but also are not always efficient to prevent chemical reaction between the fiber and matrix especially at high temperature[2].

In the paper, a new method of the altrosnic liquid infiltration is employed to manufacture Gr/Al precursor without any coating on the graphite fiber surface[3], and Gr/Al composite are produced by squeeze casting with LD2 or LD5 alloy using the new method Gr/Al precursors. When Gr/Al composite is fabricated by solid state diffusion bonding the process is operated for 30 min in the hot pressure temperature so that the interface reactions are obvious. The squeeze casting is employed to manufacture Gr/Al composite which improves the bonding between the precursor and Aluminum alloy matrix therefore the strength and modulus of Gr/Al are increased. These results can be explained by the interface reaction and it's fracture morphology of Gr/Al composites.

2. EXPERIMENT

1. Fabrication of Gr/Al precursor

The altrosnic liquid infiltration is employed to manufacture Gr/Al precursor without diffusion barrier coating on the fiber surface. Which is directly to achieve wettability between the fiber and matrix. The graphite fiber (M40) bundle is continuously drawn through a bath containing moltenaluminum depend upon the altrosnic helping the liquid aluminum is fully infiltrated into the fiber bundle. The tensile strength and modulus of Gr/al precursor are determined.

2. Manufacture of Gr/Al Composite

Gr/Al composites are produced by LD2 and LD5 alloy heating over 50-80 k of its melting point and then it is squeezed into the preform of Gr/Al precursors which pre-set up in the model and it is preheated at certain temperature. the squeeze casting parameters are given in the table 1.

Table 1. The squeeze casting technique parameters

Parameters	T _m	T _p	P	T
Materials	(K)	(K)	(MPa)	(min)
Gr/LD5	1033	773	>50	1-2
Gr/LD2	1013	773	>50	1-2

In the table 1: T_m is the temperature of liquid aluminum alloy. T_p is the temperature of preheating of Gr/Al precursors preform and the casting model. P is the squeeze casting pressure. T is the squeeze casting time. Gr/Al composites are fabricated by difference squeeze casting parameter and these squeeze casting parameters and these specimens are used to measure the tensile strength and modulus and then to study the fracture and the interface.

3. Observations of The Fracture Morphology

Gr/Al composites are fabricated by the difference squeeze casting technique parameters and the strength and modulus of Gr/Al composite specimens are measured. After failing, the specimens fracture are observed by SEM and find a great distinct caused by the difference parameters.

4. Interface Reaction Analysis

The interface of Gr/Al composite is Shown by TEM. The structure and composition of the interface are analyzed by SAED and SIMS.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Gr/Al precursor is produced by the altrosonic liquid infiltration. The strength of Gr/Al precursor is 900 MPa and the modulus is 187 GPa. The strength and modulus are not lower than the other methods produced. The squeeze casting parameters are used to manufacture Gr/LD2 and Gr/LD5 composites. The mechanical properties of Gr/LD2 and Gr/LD5 composites are determined after heat-treatment by T6.

The strength and modulus of Gr/LD2 composite are respectively 550 MPa and 130 GPa. The strength and modulus of Gr/LD5 composite are 523 MPa and 125 GPa. After tensile testing, the failure specimens are used to observe the fracture morphology by SEM.

Fig.1. a-d show the difference magnification fracture morphology of Gr/LD2 composite by squeeze casting. From Fig.1.a. we can find the LD2 alloy is sufficiently infiltrated into the precursors bundle and the fracture occurs the flange of Gr/Al precursor.

When the specimen fails the crack extension is prevented by

Gr/Al precursor and Gr/Al precursor pull out is limited. In

Fig.1. The fracture morphology of Gr/Al composite by squeeze casting.

Fig.1.b the better bounding is shown between the precursor and matrix. The dimples morphology appear around Gr/Al precursor when the specimen fails. It explains that the matrix ruptures in a ductile manner. Fig.1.c. shows the fracture morphology of the interface between two precursors. The fracture surface characteristics exhibit well defined dimple morphology but the fibers in the precursor fail in a brittle manner because of the fibers pull-out are not obviously. The well defined dimple morphology is shown in Fig.d. From the more magnification fracture a few fibers are pull-out near the interface bounding area. It explains the matrix ductile is improved during the squeeze casting in the area. The strength and modulus of Gr/Al composite are increased. If the parameters are unnormally, for example, the temperature T_m of the liquid aluminum alloy is higher or lower by squeeze casting, the quality of Gr/Al composite is not perfect and it effects the interface. The fracture morphology of Gr/Al composite is shown in Fig.2. which T_m is 1133 k for LD5.

Fig.2 The rough fracture morphology by SEM

Fig.3. The severity reaction Fracture morphology by SEM

The fracture morphology appears seriously poor ductile and where the interface dedounging between the precursor and the matrix is obviously.

Fig.3 shows a rough fracture surface and occurs a larger crystal seize which caused the lower strength and modules. The interface reaction is also shown in Fig.3. These exhibit that the temperature of squeeze casting should be not more than 1013 k and 1033 k respectively for LD2 and LD5alloy, though the higher temperature can produce excellent fluidizing and infiltrated full in the precursors bundle, but it can decrease the mechanical properties of Gr/al composite. If the temperature is lower, the liquid alloy fluidizing is not good enough for squeeze casting, the perfect performance of Gr/Al composite is also not obtained.

The squeeze casting pressure P is one more important parameter. The fracture morphology of the porosity is shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4. The fracture morphology of porous of Gr/Al composite by squeeze casting

Fig.5. The interface of Gr/Al composite by TEM.

It is caused by the squeeze casting pressure P is lower than 50 MPa and the liquid alloy can not be fully infiltrated into Gr/Al precursors bundle. Otherwise, the parameters of the preheating temperature T_p of the precursors preform and the model as well as the time T of control constant pressure during the squeeze casting are very important too for the performance of Gr/Al composite. The interface of Gr/Al composite using the squeeze casting is shown in Fig.5. by TEM. The SAED is used to define the matrix alloy, graphite fiber and the interface which is clearly shown in the middle of Fig.5. which shows that the bonding between the fiber and matrix is very good.

The selected area electron diffraction patterns are employed to analysis of the reaction products of the interface and the products Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 are found but no Al_4C_3 is occurred.

The spectrogram of SIMAS is used to determine the reaction products by the squeeze casting process and points that C^+ , O^+ , Si^+ , Al^+ , Mg^+ and AlC^+ etc, and some oxide ions of the metals. It explains the reaction between the matrix and graphite fiber is no more seriously at the proper parameters by the squeeze casting because the process time is very short only operates in 1-2min.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The squeeze casting processes is employed to manufacture Gr/Al composite using the precursors produced by the ultrasonic liquid infiltration is more effective than the other methods and it no detracts the environments.
2. The strength and modulus of Gr/LD2 composite are respectively 550 MPa and 130 GPa and Gr/LD5 are 523MPa and 125GPa .
3. The fracture morphology and its performance have a direct relationship to the technique parameters.
4. SAED and SIMS analysis point that the interface reaction is not seriously, because the operation time is only 1-2 min and no Al_4C_3 is found at the interface.

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